

POULTRY NUTRITION AND MANAGEMENT: A HOLISTIC APPROACH FOR SUSTAINABLE PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT

Poultry nutrition and management are vital for modern production, directly affecting growth, egg yield, feed efficiency, flock health and welfare. Optimal productivity and economic sustainability depend on the provision of a balanced diet that fulfils the physiological and metabolic requirements of birds. The six essential nutrient classes-water, carbohydrates, proteins, fats, minerals, and vitamins-collectively regulate metabolism, immunity, and overall performance. Nutrient requirements vary with species, breed, age, production stage, and environment (summer, winter). Recent advances in feed formulation, ingredient evaluation, and precision nutrition have greatly enhanced feed efficiency and resource utilization. Equally critical are effective management practices that includes biosecurity, environmental control, housing design, and feed quality monitoring, which collectively enhance nutrient utilization. This article elucidates the scientific principles underlying poultry nutrition, integrates nutritional and management strategies, and highlights emerging innovations such as enzyme supplementation, nutrigenomics, and sustainable feed alternatives that collectively improve productivity, quality, and environmental sustainability in poultry sector.

KEYWORDS: Poultry, Nutrition, Protein, Metabolism, Diseases

INTRODUCTION

Poultry farming plays a crucial component in the livestock sector “food-producing farm animals” in protein world (National Protein Day February 27th), contributing significantly to nutritional security, employment generation, and rural economic development. India holds a prominent global position, ranking second in egg production (142.77 billion) and fifth in poultry meat (5.018 million tons) production (BAHS, 2024). The country's meat market was valued at approximately INR 1959.5 billion in 2022 and projected to grow at compound annually by 9.2% from 2023-28, reaching about INR 3133.41 billion by 2028 (CAGR Annual Report, 2023). The Indian poultry sector includes three main segments: commercial producers, small and marginal farmers, and backyard poultry keepers. Backyard and small-scale units provide vital nutrition and additional income for rural households, while commercial farms meet growing consumer demand through organized production systems. Together, these interlinked sectors form a dynamic and resilient poultry industry that uniquely integrates subsistence and commercial models.

Over the past few decades, Indian poultry farming has evolved from backyard rearing into a modern, technology-driven industry. This transformation is fueled by private investment, better infrastructure, and advances in breeding, feeding, and disease control. Increasing poultry consumption reflects urbanization, higher incomes, and changing food habits. Despite progress, feed management remains a major challenge (60-80% of production costs). Rising feed prices and inconsistent ingredient quality often limit productivity, particularly for smallholders. Moreover, India's diverse agro-ecological conditions and irregular resource availability affect feed supply and quality. Overcoming these nutritional and management challenges is crucial for ensuring sustainable growth, profitability, and efficiency in the rapidly expanding poultry sector.

CONTEMPORARY STATUS OF FEED RESOURCE AVAILABILITY AND UTILIZATION IN POULTRY FARMING

The productivity and profitability of poultry farming depend largely on bird genetics, management practices, environmental conditions and most importantly, the adequacy and efficiency of nutrition. Among these factors, nutrition represents the single most critical and cost-intensive input, directly influence on growth rate, feed conversion efficiency, reproductive performance, and overall flock health. Feed alone contributes approximately 65–70% of total production costs in broilers and 75–80% in layers, underscoring its major economic importance and efficient feed formulation in the poultry enterprise (Samuel Olugbenga *et al.*, 2015).

In India and worldwide, maize (king of feed) provides energy (60% inclusion), and soybean meal (40%-queen of feed) supplies protein (35-40% inclusion) in poultry diets. However, their production lags behind industry growth, with rising competition from food and industrial sectors. Hence, diversifying feed resources and identifying alternative energy- and protein-rich ingredients is essential to sustain efficient and balanced poultry production.

Cereals and oilseeds traditionally used in poultry ration, faces growing competition from human consumption driven by urbanization, population growth, and shrinking farmland. This imbalance may reduce the availability of conventional feed ingredients, raising feed costs and retail prices of eggs and meat. Rising prices could limit poultry access for low-income groups, worsening protein deficiencies (present India 141th rank in protein availability with 61.8-63.4 gm/day/person). To address this challenge, sustainable and integrative approach that includes exploring non-conventional feed resources, improving feed conversion efficiency, and developing cost-effective, eco-friendly formulations.

Promising strategies to reduce feed costs include utilization of agro-industrial by-products (rice bran, cassava peel, and oilseed cakes) and novel ingredients (insect meal, algae, and single-cell proteins). However, the practical use of these alternatives is often constrained by nutritional variability, anti-nutritional factors, processing challenges, and limited farmer awareness. Advances in feed processing technologies, including enzyme supplementation, extrusion, and fermentation, have shown potential to enhance nutrient availability and digestibility. Specifically, exogenous enzymes such as phytase, xylanase,

and β -glucanase improve the utilization of structural carbohydrates and phytate phosphorus, thereby reducing nutrient waste and mitigating wet litter problems (Reddy, 2018). Furthermore, errors in feed formulation, improper mixing and storage can cause nutrient imbalances, reduced efficiency, and economic loss. Ensuring quality control, accurate formulation, and farmer training is crucial. Strong collaboration among scientists, feed technologists, policymakers, and feed industry is essential to develop sustainable feeding systems that enhance productivity, profitability, and environmental sustainability in modern poultry production.

INNOVATIVE NUTRITIONAL STRATEGIES TO ENHANCE FEED EFFICIENCY AND REDUCE PRODUCTION COST

Feed cost is the largest expense in poultry production, comprising 60-80% of total production cost. Therefore, reducing feed expenditure is a critical strategy to enhance profitability, resource utilization, and overall production efficiency. Economic poultry farming can be achieved through scientifically designed nutritional and management interventions that optimize feed efficiency without compromising bird health or productivity. The key strategies are outlined below.

1. Timed Feeding in Broilers

Broilers are commonly provided unrestricted access/ *ad libitum* to feed to attain market weight rapidly. However, controlled or timed feeding has been shown to improve feed efficiency and nutrient utilization. In this system, birds receive measured feed portions four to six times daily, with one-hour fasting intervals. This method minimizes continuous gut stimulation which is typical in *ad libitum* feeding. During fasting intervals, birds remain calm and less active, decreasing maintenance energy requirements and improving nutrient absorption efficiency. Consequently, timed feeding supports better feed conversion ratio (FCR) and reduced overall feed wastage.

2. Use of Synthetic Amino Acids and Enzymes

Protein sources are among the most expensive components of poultry diets, particularly in protein-deficient tropical countries such as India. To minimize costs while maintaining optimal performance, rations should be formulated to supply limiting amino acids-

primarily lysine and methionine (ideal amino acid concept) at levels sufficient for the desired production rate. Supplementing diets with synthetic amino acids (approximately 250g per ton feed) can substitute for high-protein ingredients, thereby reducing overall feed costs without affecting productivity.

Furthermore, exogenous enzymes have emerged as vital tools in modern feed technology to enhance nutrient digestibility and lower feed expenses. These biotechnological interventions significantly improve feed utilization efficiency and reduce the dependency on costly conventional feed ingredients.

- i. Phytase improves phosphorus availability by hydrolyzing phytate complexes, thereby reducing the need for costly inorganic phosphorus supplements.
- ii. Protease enhances the breakdown of plant proteins and reduces the effects of anti-nutritional factors present in soybean meal and other protein sources.
- iii. Amylase and xylanase improve carbohydrate digestion, increasing the available metabolizable energy by approximately 3–5% when incorporated into diets.

3. Control of Feed Wastage

Feed wastage is a major contributor to economic losses in poultry enterprises. Preventing unnecessary feed loss requires attention to equipment design, feeding management, and storage conditions (Chandrasekaran and Raghuram, 2014).

- i. **Feeder Design**
Traditional galvanized metal troughs are prone to feed spillage and physical damage. Replacing them with automatic or chain feeder systems can reduce mechanical losses and ensure uniform feed distribution.
- ii. **Feed Level Management**
Maintaining feed at an optimal level within the trough is essential. Overfilling feeders encourages wastage through scattering, while underfilling limits intake and growth performance.
- iii. **Beak Trimming**
Untrimmed beaks can lead to feed scattering and wastage, as birds tend to “play” with feed rather than consume it. Beak trimming, when performed correctly, not only minimizes feed spillage but also

reduces injurious behaviors such as cannibalism and feather pecking.

iv. **Feed Storage and Quality Control**

In tropical regions characterized by high temperature and humidity, feed is susceptible to mold growth and nutrient degradation if improperly stored. The inclusion of 0.5% calcium aluminum silicate acts as an effective mycotoxin binder, maintaining feed quality and bird health. Additionally, the use of silo-based storage systems helps prevent moisture accumulation, contamination, and spoilage of feed ingredients.

4. Integrated Nutritional Management

Feed cost reduction should not rely on a single intervention but rather on a holistic feeding strategy that combines efficient nutrient formulation, precision feeding, and improved feed handling practices. Regular monitoring of feed conversion ratio (FCR), nutrient digestibility, and bird performance indicators allows producers to make data-driven adjustments that enhance profitability. Collaboration between nutritionists, veterinarians, and farm managers is essential to implement these cost-effective feeding systems sustainably.

Incorporation of Feed Additives and Alternative Nutrients in Poultry Diets

1. Incorporation of Flavouring Agents

Feed flavouring agents can improve feed intake and growth in poultry. Studies show birds fed flavoured diets gained about 8 g more at four weeks and 3 g more at eight weeks than controls, with better feed conversion ratios. These additives enhance palatability, reduce feed rejection, and promote higher productivity and efficient nutrient utilization in flocks.

2. Utilization of Unconventional Feed Ingredients

Unconventional feedstuffs are non-traditional feed resources (NCFRs) possess potential nutritional value with organic in nature, locally available, low economic value, but vary with collection, processing, and transportation costs. Though rich in nutrients, some may contain anti-nutritional factors (ANF) or toxic factors, requiring proper processing and controlled inclusion. Their effective use can reduce reliance on conventional feed ingredients and help overcome feed shortages, especially in developing regions.

A. Alternative Energy Sources

Potential unconventional energy sources includes oil-extracted seed meals and seed flours, tapioca flour, dried poultry waste, molasses, minor or small millets. These ingredients can serve as partial substitutes for cereal grains such as maize, contributing metabolizable energy when formulated appropriately.

B. Alternative Plant Protein Sources

Several oilseed by-products and non-traditional legumes provide valuable plant-based protein supplementation, including, mustard cake, soy flour, sesame flour, sunflower seed meal, safflower meal, niger (ramtil) cake, karanja or pongamia glabra cake. Proper detoxification or processing (heat treatment, soaking) is essential to inactivate ANF (glucosinolates, tannins) before inclusion in feed formulations. (Ravindran and Blair, 1992).

C. Alternative Animal Protein Sources

Unconventional animal-origin proteins can effectively replace or complement fish meal in poultry diets. Commonly utilized by-products include, blood meal, liver meal, feather meal (after hydrolysis), poultry by-product meal, hatchery by-product meal.

These ingredients provide key nutrients but require strict hygiene and quality control to ensure safety.

The judicious use of flavoring agents and scientifically processed unconventional feed ingredients offers a sustainable approach to reduce feed costs, improve nutrient utilization, and enhance productivity in economic poultry production systems.

CONCLUSION

The shortage of quality feed resources remains a key challenge in poultry production, demanding strategic nutritional management for sustainability and profitability. Bridging the gap between feed demand and supply requires innovative solutions, including non-conventional feed resources, flavour enhancers, protein supplements, and feed enzymes to improve feed efficiency and reduce production costs. Though adoption of alternatives remains limited, advances in feed technology and biotechnology offer strong potential. Continued innovation and knowledge dissemination, and scientific application can help the poultry industry overcome nutritional challenges and achieve sustainable cost-effective growth.

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